

BOOK REVIEW

Festus Adedayo. *Ayinla Omowura: Life and Times of an Apala Legend*
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Reviewer: Stephen T. Ogunidipe

stogundipe@oauife.edu.ng

Festus Adedayo's *Ayinla Omowura: Life and Times of an Apala Legend* is the first single-author study devoted to the Yoruba Apala musician Ayinla Omowura and his legacy. Writing four decades after Ayinla died in 1980, Adedayo traces the musician's life across seven chronologically organised chapters, from the origins of Apala music through Ayinla's emergence and iconic years as an established artist. Drawing on his journalistic background, Adedayo employs a reportorial narrative style to examine one of the leading voices in 1970s Yoruba music. The author categorically states that “this book is not a hagiography on Ayinla Omowura... the aim was to present the totality of his life—the good, the bad and the ugly” (13). He demonstrates critical mastery of his subject, weaving together personal interviews, historical records and in-depth examination of Omowura's lyrics to paint a rich picture of the artist's life. This approach enables readers to connect with the cultural and social context that influenced Omowura's music and understand its broad appeal.

Understanding Ayinla Omowura requires realising the inseparability of Yoruba culture and music. In Yoruba society, music is not merely entertainment but a vital aspect of social, religious and political life, playing essential roles in rituals, festivals and everyday activities as a powerful tool for communication, education and unity. Adedayo emphasises this cultural foundation in his opening chapter, illustrating music's central role in African life. His subject, Ayinla Omowura, was born in the 1930s and became one of the most significant voices in the Yoruba popular music scene of the 1970s. His music, deeply rooted in Yoruba culture, delivered social commentary through lyrics that addressed morality, societal values and the experiences of ordinary people. The renewed contemporary interest in Omowura is evident in Tunde Kelani's 2021 film *Ayinla*, which garnered significant attention domestically and internationally, introducing new audiences, both Yoruba and non-Yoruba speakers, to Omowura's music.

Adedayo's methodological strengths are evident in his lyrical analysis and contextualisation. He dissects Omowura's lyrics to reveal their underlying social and political themes, demonstrating how the musician addressed issues such as hypocrisy and corruption. The translations and commentary explain both the symbolic and literal meanings of Omowura's words. By situating Omowura within the sociopolitical climate of 1970s Nigeria, the author illustrates how the musician's work was both a product of and a response to his environment. This contextualization helps readers appreciate Omowura's impact on his audience and the enduring relevance of his music.

The book also examines Omowura's fiery temperament, which became integral to his public persona. As Adedayo notes, Omowura was known for his no-nonsense approach to disputes, and “his temper was as quick as his wit, and this duality defined much of his personal and professional life.” The author contrasts Omowura's musical brilliance with the darker aspects of his personality, fulfilling his stated goal of presenting “the totality of his life.”

Adedayo's approach reflects his journalistic background and his established authority on Omowura, having been a longtime promoter of the musician's work. He conducted extensive interviews with individuals who could help distinguish myth from fact, making efforts to contact every living person who could contribute meaningfully to the discourse. The book functions not only as a biography but also as a literary and critical analysis, dwelling extensively on Omowura's artistic ability and his contributions to societal and cultural development. For instance, chapter four opens with translations of Omowura's songs that illustrate his lyrical sophistication.

Adedayo employs precise and elegant language that enhances the reading experience. Through rich descriptive prose, he brings historical events, personal flaws, and triumphs alive on the page, allowing readers to immerse themselves fully in the narrative. The inclusion of photographs significantly enhances the biography, adding a visual dimension that complements the storytelling. Images of Omowura provide readers with tangible connections to the subject, capturing key moments and stages of his journey. By including photographs of interview respondents, the author allows readers to connect faces to names, enhancing the credibility of the account. This biography represents a significant contribution to scholarship on Ayinla Omowura. Before this work, little substantial

writing on Omowura existed beyond undergraduate projects, making Adedayo's study an important intervention in documenting this influential figure.

Despite its considerable strengths, the biography has notable limitations. The subjectivity of some respondents presents challenges to accuracy. Elderly interviewees, such as Adewole Onilu (Ayinla's lead drummer), struggled with recalling events accurately, potentially introducing biases or inaccuracies into the narrative. This reliance on potentially unreliable memories can detract from the biography's credibility, though Adedayo makes efforts to corroborate information across multiple sources.

The book's considerable length, 537 pages, raises accessibility concerns. While Adedayo's desire to provide a comprehensive account is understandable, dedicating excessive space to appraising Omowura's work can lead to reader fatigue. The level of detail, while informative for specialists, may not be necessary for a general audience. The author could have streamlined the content by focusing on the most significant works and providing concise evaluations without excessive detail. Some of the more granular appraisals could have been placed in an appendix for readers particularly interested in detailed analysis.

Moreover, the author's emphasis on negative aspects of Omowura's character (evident on pages 67, 77, 83, 90, 106, and elsewhere) creates a significant imbalance. While presenting a balanced view is essential for biography, the heavy emphasis on Ayinla's shortcomings and challenges can overshadow his achievements and positive contributions. At times, this focus risks making the narrative one-dimensional, potentially skewing readers' perception of the subject.

The journalistic approach, while enabling a thorough and unsparing study, has significant limitations in terms of scholarly rigour. The reportorial style prioritises narrative accessibility and chronological storytelling over the theoretical frameworks, methodological transparency and sustained critical analysis that characterise academic monographs. Adedayo does not engage substantially with existing scholarship on Yoruba music, popular culture studies or biographical methodology, nor does he situate his work within broader intellectual conversations about cultural memory, postcolonial identity or the politics of musical representation. The book lacks critical distance at times, with the author's evident admiration for Omowura occasionally undermining

analytical objectivity. Furthermore, the reliance on oral testimony without sufficient source criticism or acknowledgement of the constructed nature of memory raises methodological concerns. While the journalistic approach offers immediacy and accessibility, it forgoes the interpretive depth and theoretical sophistication that would strengthen the work's scholarly contribution. However, Adedayo's journalistic background also provides unique advantages, including his ability to conduct extensive interviews, his narrative skill in making the subject compelling for general readers and his established credibility as a longtime authority on Omowura's work.

Despite these limitations, the book remains a valuable resource offering a detailed exploration of Ayinla Omowura's life and works. By refining the interview methodology, balancing the portrayal more evenly and trimming the volume, it could have been a more compelling and accessible biography. Nevertheless, Adedayo has produced a commendable work that fills a significant gap in the literature and offers important insights into one of Nigeria's most influential musicians.